

Simulation of Thermoconvective Flows as Applied to Design of Water Cooling Tower by Use of Mixture Model

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Thermoconvective flows are investigated on base of solution of 3D conservation equations in approximation of mixture model. Hyperbolic cooling tower is under consideration. Natural convection inside the design of a hyperbolic cooling tower depending on the temperature of the inside wall is considered. The values of the velocity field and the maximum velocity of the vapor-air flow are obtained.

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1. Introduction

Although Hyperbolic cool towers are more expensive than other normal tower types, they are used extensively in the field of electric nuclear power generation (Figure 1). The purpose of the work is: to determine the organization of the thermoconvective flows in the Hyperbolic cooling tower in the working state and without a drop structure, to develop a model for calculating the thermconvective flows in the cooling tower based on the solution of the 3D system of non-stationary conservation equations. Accepted mixture model is regarded as a single flowing continuum with macroscopic properties such as density and viscosity. The two phases consist of one dispersed phase (droplet of water) and one continuous phase (vapor-air mix). Calculations on formation of thermo-convective flow in cooling tower with and without drop structure are performed.

The relevance of the work consists in the creation of a physical and mathematical model of the formation of convective flow taking into account the temperature of the inside walls

of the cooling tower. As a result we can perform calculations with different temperature for boundary conditions on the inside surface of the cooling tower and evaluate the dependence of the maximum flow rate in the nonoperating cooling tower on the temperature for the selected boundary conditions. As a result of the numerical model, the dependence of the maximum speed in the cooling tower volume on the value of the temperature gradient on the inside walls was obtained. This dependence is used as an initial condition when starting the cooling tower and has an impact on the efficiency of the wet cooling tower.

To solve the problem, a model of vapor-air flow heat and mass transfer processes was developed, taking into account the drop structure in relation to the operating conditions of the cooling tower. Initial and boundary conditions have been defined for the selected calculation area. The developed model takes into account the values of thermophysical parameters of the vapor-air medium with and without a drop structure inside the cooling tower volume. Estimated calculations were made for the number of thermoconvective flows within the cooling tower volume for various values of the cooling tower operation parameters.

A cooling tower of the Belarusian nuclear

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power plant (NPP) was selected for modeling. Cooling towers are designed to discharge heat into the environment from the NPP condensers.

One cooling tower per unit is provided at the Belarusian NPP. The height of the cooling tower is 167 m, the diameter of the base is 128.4 m, the diameter of the outlet section is 80.9 m. This cooling tower is the highest cooling tower in Belarus.

The diagram of the cooling tower arrangement and its principle of operation are shown in Figure 1. The operation of the tower cooling tower is based on the natural air draft created by the pressure difference at the bottom and top of the tower. The cooled water is supplied through the inlet manifold to a water distribution system located at the base of the tower, where it is sprayed with nozzles over the entire water distribution area. In the area of water distribution, water is crushed into small drops. Thus, in the water distributor layer, a process of the water evaporation occurs with a decrease in temperature [1].

FIG. 1: (Color online) Wet Cooling Tower Arrangement Diagram.

In the main cooling system, cooled water from the cooling tower basin is supplied through a closed supply channel to the pump station of the turbine building, passes through the rotating water treatment networks of the pumps, and is supplied to the turbine condensers by pumps through the supply water ducts. The water heated in the condensers is supplied to the cooling tower

through discharge water ducts for cooling [2].

At the same time, an empirical relationship is observed: 1 percent of the evaporated liquid is cooled by the remaining 99 percent by 5.7 °C. On average, the open cooling tower evaporates about 2 percent of the incoming water.

Under different initial conditions (temperature and humidity), the evaporative cooling tower removes a different amount of heat, that is, it provides a certain temperature of cooling water at the inlet to the condenser. If water with a lower temperature flows from the cooling tower to the condenser, then a more or less low back pressure is achieved in the condenser, which contributes to the greater work performed by the turbine. In this way, detailed modeling of the heat and mass exchange processes of the cooling tower volume will make it possible to determine the rational operating conditions of the nuclear power plant.

2. Computed Region Model in COMSOL Environment

The description of thermoconvective flows for complicated cooling tower design is based on the solution of non-stationary conservation equations for mixture model approximation. Conservation equations for individual components of the vapor-air continues medium and the water droplet disperse media are used for description of conditions of multi-component medium. The mixture model was built in the COMSOL software environment (Figure 2). The geometric dimensions of the design area correspond to the real characteristics.

A grid is specified for the model. The grid pitch is chosen so that the main calculations are carried out inside the cooling tower and near its walls (Figure 3).

The initial system of 3D conservation equations taking into account the calculation of thermophysical parameters according to the Mixture model [3] approximation is as follows:

FIG. 2: Settlement area 400x400x450 m.

FIG. 3: Finite element partitioned computation domain.

$$\frac{\partial \rho W_i}{\partial x_i} = 0, \quad (1)$$

where index i denotes the summation of three

coordinates in a 3D approximation.

$$\frac{\partial W_i}{\partial t} + W_j \frac{\partial W_i}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\nu_E \frac{\partial W_i}{\partial x_j} - \overline{W_i' W_j'} \right), \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + W_j \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\alpha_E \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_j} \right), \quad (3)$$

where

$$\overline{W_i' W_j'} = -\nu_E \left(\frac{\partial W_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial W_j}{\partial x_i} \right) - \frac{2}{3} \delta_{ij} K_j, \quad (4)$$

with W_i is the components of the velocity of the transportation flow along the axes x_i , x_j (in this model $i, j = 1, 2, 3$, $i \neq j$; x_1, x_2, x_3 is the spatial coordinates); P , T pressure, temperature; ρ density; g acceleration of gravity; ν coefficients of kinematic viscosity; α coefficient of thermal conductivity; K turbulent kinetic energy according to the k - ϵ turbulence model; index E effective value taking into account the model of turbulence.

To describe the process of transfer of dispersed radionuclides in the stream, the original system of the conservation equation (1BТ“3) is supplemented by the equations of motion and conservation of aerosol particles:

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(D \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_j} \right) = R, \quad (5)$$

with $\frac{\partial C}{\partial t}$ is the change in moisture concentration over time; $D \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_j}$ is the change due to convection and diffusion; R is the change due to the formation of new droplets; C dispersed phase concentration.

To calculate thermophysical parameters of the vapor-gas mixture, the conservation equations are supplemented with formulas [4]:

$$\rho_{mix} = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{\rho_g} + \left(\frac{1}{\rho''} - \frac{1}{\rho_g} \right) C''}, \quad (6)$$

$$C''_{Sf} = C''_S = \frac{1}{\left(\frac{m}{m''} \right) \left(\frac{p_0}{p_S} - 1 \right)}, \quad (7)$$

Empirical dependence of water vapor saturation pressure on temperature [5]:

$$P_S = 2.235 \cdot T \cdot \exp \left\{ \frac{15.7 + (T - 273)}{T - 46.5} \right\}, \quad (8)$$

$$m_{mix} = \frac{1}{\frac{C''}{m''} + \frac{1-C''}{m_S}}, \quad (9)$$

$$X_g = (1 - C'') \frac{m_{mix}}{m_g}, \quad (10)$$

$$X'' = C'' \frac{m_{mix}}{m''}, \quad (11)$$

$$X_g = 1 - X'', \quad (12)$$

$$\rho_g = \frac{P_0 \cdot m_g \cdot 10^{-5}}{0.08314 \cdot T}, \quad (13)$$

$$\rho'' = \frac{P_0 \cdot m'' \cdot 10^{-5}}{0.08314 \cdot T}, \quad (14)$$

$$\mu_{mix} = \mu'' \cdot X'' + \mu_g \cdot X_g, \quad (15)$$

$$\lambda_{mix} = \lambda'' \cdot X'' + \lambda_g \cdot X_g, \quad (16)$$

$$(C_p)_{mix} = C'' \cdot C_p'' + C_{pg} \cdot C_g, \quad (17)$$

with C_n is the concentration of water vapors; J source term; q heat exchange intensity; k latent heat of evaporation; ρ_{mix} density of vapor-gas mixture; ρ_g gas density; ρ'' vapor density; C'' vapor concentration; C_S'' saturated vapor concentration; m_{mix} molecular weight of the mixture; m'' molecular weight of vapor; m_S molecular weight of vapor; X_g mass concentration of gas; X'' mass concentration of vapor; μ_{mix} dynamic viscosity coefficient of vapor-gas mixture; μ'' dynamic vapor viscosity coefficient; μ_g dynamic air viscosity coefficient; λ_{mix} coefficient of heat conductivity of vapor-gas

mix; λ'' coefficient of heat conductivity of vapor; λ_g coefficient of heat conductivity of gas.

The intensity of heat exchange and mass exchange for dispersed particles is determined by the coefficient of heat transfer α mass transfer β or by dimensionless parameters Nu and the Sherwood number Sh [5]:

$$q = \pi d_k^2 \alpha (T'' - T_k), \quad (18)$$

$$Nu = \frac{d_k \alpha}{\lambda''} = 2 + 0.64 Re^{1/2} Pr^{0.33}, \quad (19)$$

$$Q = \pi d_k^2 \beta (T_k - T''), \quad (20)$$

$$Sh = \frac{d_k \beta}{D} = +0.64 Re^{1/2} Sc^{0.33}, \quad (21)$$

with Re is the Reynolds number; Pr is the Prandtl number; Sc is the Schmidt number; πd_k^2 droplet surface area; α heat transfer coefficient; T'' ambient temperature; T_k droplet surface temperature; d_k droplet diameter; β mass transfer coefficient; D diffusion coefficient.

The boundary conditions are that the velocity on the walls of the cooling tower is 0, the temperature is equal to the temperature of the inside wall.

During calculations, the concentration of vapor C'' is compared with the concentration of saturated vapors C_S'' , calculated at the separation temperature. If there is an excess of the calculated concentration value relative to the saturated vapor concentration at any point of the calculated region ($C'' > C_S''$), then the water vapors condense in the air volume.

Figure 4 shows the results of the temperature field calculations at the inside wall temperature of the 360 K cooling tower and the ambient temperature of 293 K. The speed field of the same set of data is shown in Figure 5.

The following notions are used in the figures: max is the point of maximum flow velocity, min is the point of minimum flow velocity, $rhomax$ is the point of maximum vapor-gas density, $rhomin$ is the point of minimum vapor-gas density.

FIG. 4: (Color online) Isosurface temperatures in the cooling tower volume at the temperature of the inside wall of the cooling tower 360 K and ambient temperature 293 K. The red arrows indicate flow direction.

The velocity field and the temperature field were calculated at different external wind flow rates. Figure 6 shows the results of the calculation at maximum external speed at a height of 500 m is equal to 10 m/s. Figure 7 shows the results of the calculation at maximum external speed at a height of 500 m is equal to 20 m/s. In the calculations, the temperature of the inner surface of the cooling tower walls was accepted at 295 K. In this case, the max flow velocity inside the cooling tower reaches 12.5 m/s.

As a result of numerical simulation, it was obtained that a structure of vapor-air flow inside and outside of cooling tower depends on the values of external wind flow (Figure 6 and Figure 7).

In addition, as a result of numerical simulation, the dependence of the maximum velocity of the vapor-air flow inside the Hyperbolic cooling tower versus the value of the temperature on the inside surface of the cooling tower was obtained. When the temperature of the inside wall of the cooling tower is equal to 295 K, the calculated maximum velocity inside the tower

FIG. 5: (Color online) Maximum speed in the cooling tower volume at the temperature of the inside wall of the cooling tower 360 K and ambient temperature 293 K. The red arrows indicate flow direction. The color chart displays a field of velocities from zero (white) to 16 m/s (black).

is 13 m/s, but when the temperature of the inside wall of the cooling tower is 360 K, the maximum velocity of vapor-air mixture inside the tower is equal to 18 m/s (Figure 8). The calculation results are shown in the diagram in Figure 8.

Based on mixture model, a physical and mathematical model of the formation of a thermoconvective convective flow for the hyperbolic cooling tower in the working state and without a drop structure was developed. The mixture model allows the calculation of vapor-gas-liquid flows based on the solution of the equations of conservation of mass, energy and momentum, taking into account the closure relations and the corresponding initial and boundary conditions. The system of equations is solved numerically in a non-stationary formulation until a quasi-stationary state is reached.

Calculations of the velocity field and

FIG. 6: (Color online) Isosurfaces of temperature and velocity field around cooling tower at an external wind speed of 10 m/s. Ambient temperature is equal 295 293 K, the max temperature inside tower is equal 295 K

FIG. 7: (Color online) Isosurfaces of temperature and velocity field around cooling tower at an external wind speed of 10 m/s. Ambient temperature is equal 295 293 K, the max temperature inside tower is equal 295 K

temperature field were made at different speeds of the external wind flow. The difference between the cooling tower weathering and the external wind speed is shown graphically. Calculations were made with different temperatures for boundary conditions on the inner surface of the cooling tower and the dependence of the maximum flow rate in the non-operating cooling tower on the temperature for the selected boundary conditions was estimated. As a result of numerical modeling, the dependence of the maximum speed in the cooling tower volume on the value of the temperature gradient on the inner walls was obtained. At a wall temperature of 293 K, a flow is created inside the cooling tower at a speed of 13 m/s, and at a wall temperature of 310 K, a flow is created inside the cooling tower at a speed of 16 m/s. The flow rate inside the cooling tower is shown to increase as the temperature on the walls of the cooling tower increases. It follows that even a small temperature gradient in the walls leads to noticeable convective flows that affect the

FIG. 8: Diagram of the change in the maximum flow rate in the cooling tower volume depending on the temperature of the inside wall of the cooling tower.

efficiency of the hyperbolic cooling tower.

The studies carried out will allow simulating in detail the operation of the wet cooling tower and clarifying the calculation results taking into account the initial thermoconvective flows.

3. Conclusion

Research and development of cooling towers for nuclear power plants is an urgent task to ensure efficient and safe cooling of the power plant. Within the framework of the work, a model for calculating the thermoconvective flow in the cooling tower was developed based on the solution of the 3D system of nonstationary equations, taking into account the conservation equations for individual components of the vapor-air medium and the dispersed water structure on the basis of the mixture model. Calculations were made to form a thermoconvective flow in the Hyperbolic cooling tower for different various operating modes. Physical and mathematical models were

developed for the formation of a convective flow, taking into account the temperature of the walls inside of the cooling tower. The maximum cooling tower velocity rate vs the temperature of inside wall of Hyperbolic cooling tower was obtained. It has been shown that even a small temperature gradient on the inside walls leads to noticeable convective flows, which affect the efficiency of the cooling tower. From the analysis of the obtained physically consistent numerical results, it can be concluded that the results of this study can be used as the basis for further improvement of the proposed model and the software module for analyzing the data obtained at the cooling tower of the nuclear power plant.

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